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THE REVELATION OF VIRTUE THROUGH EVIL IN THE SHORT STORY “A FRIEND IN NEED” BY WILLIAM SOMERSET MAUGHAM

Pulatova Sabina Sharifovna

A teacher of Foreign Languages Department, Pedagogical Institute of Bukhara State University, Uzbekistan

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes how Somerset Maugham’s short story “A Friend in Need” skillfully reflects the power and value of true friendship using ethical concepts such as goodness, kindness, justice, and compassion, which are sacred to each of us.

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Somerset Maugham is a British novelist, playwright, short story writer, highest paid author in the world in the 1930s. ¹Maugham’s skill in handling the plot has been compared with the manner of Guy de Maupassant. His stories are told in clear, economical style with cynical or resigned undertone.

“I have never pretended to be anything but a story teller. It has amused me to tell stories and I have told a great many. It is a misfortune for me that telling of a story just for the sake of the story is not an activity that is in favor with intelligentsia. In endeavor to bear my misfortunes with

¹ [Interpretation of valuable moral concepts in the novel of Somerset Maugham “The Moon and Sixpence”](#)

fortitude."²

A talented and brilliant English writer of the XX century Somerset Maugham contributed to the development of English Literature with his masterpieces like "Of Human Bondage", "The Theatre", "the Moon and Sixpence" and "The Razor's Edge".³ He leads his readers to the complicated inner world of characters making them to change their attitude towards life in his literary great works. The author's vital and clear style of expressing his thoughts, depicting events in the plot and giving characteristics to the heroes supply his works to be read with great interest and enthusiasm.

Goodness, purity, virtue... These notions are very sacred among people who know the virtual meaning of this transient life. As for the significance of such worth ethical conceptions in every society, they are voted in any nation's literature. The matter of being honest and pure was the central theme from the old times in literature. And, of course, this is a crucial issue in the literary works of many authors, and even in their masterpieces, expressed in a variety of ways. One of such writers is Somerset Maugham who revealed his ideas and thoughts about purity and friendship skillfully through malice which was a unique way of conveying virtue at that time.

The short story "A Friend in Need" is commonly dedicated to people's attitude to each other that includes not only kindness and friendship but also evil deeds and wickedness simultaneously. There are three main characters in the story, for example, the author who narrates the whole story in the first person clearly reveals his tone, his attitude towards the protagonists, another one is Edward Hide Burton, the great merchant in Kobe, and the last one is the main victim of the story Lenny Burton. Although the play has only three protagonists and the plot line is very short and not rich in events, the essence and moral of the work are extensive.

The writer gives a philosophical view to the entire meaning of the story in such way that whole its consequence comes from only action of Edward Burton. "*He was a tiny little fellow, very slender, with white hair; a red face much wrinkled, and blue eyes appearance. Though he was a sensible and an optimistic person, his character was different and strange as the author mentioned.*"⁴ The reason was that he considered Lenny Burton's death to be a very funny incident that he himself had caused. On the other hand, Lenny Burton was always well-dressed, handsome in a way, with curly hair and pink-and-white cheeks outside, and he drank too much, a bit of money used to come in for him once a quarter, he made a bit more by card-playing as well. When he went broke, the offer of swimming for the sake of Shioya Club was made by Edward as if it would be the require mental appointment for giving him vacancy in Edward Burton's office. Then, Lenny agreed for he had not another way, but as he had ruined his health by drinking alcohol, he drowned among the currents round the beacon.

It is interesting to note that even though Edward had known Lenny's death beforehand, he encouraged him to fulfill it. Automatically, reader wants to ask WHY??? It seems to the reader that Edward Burton is cruel and malicious man. But, from another point of view he is very kind and

² Somerset Maugham. *Creatures of Circumstance*. London-1947. Page-56.

³ SUPERIORITY OF MORAL IDEAS AND FATAL RESULTS OF IMMORALITY IN THE SHORT STORY OF SOMERSET MAUGHAM "THE BOOK BAG"

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⁴ Somerset Maugham. *Casuarina Tree. A Collection of short stories*. London.-1994. Page-8

sensible that he was the main stick made Lenny die honorably. If there had not been an offer like that Lenny Burton would have died from drinking too much, anyway. Therefore, it should be considered a great virtue that the only cause of the honorable death of a person whose body was alive, but he had already fallen spiritually.

The aim of the present study was to determine whether an association exists between the duration of menopause and the age of menopause onset, and the differences in bone mineral density (BMD) in postmenopausal women.⁵

A special place in the work of Utkir Khashimov is occupied by the novel “Between Two Doors”. The writer is concerned not only with the pressing social issues of today, but with eternal moral problems. In particular, by calling “Between Two Doors”, the writer means the path of person, which he walked from birth to death.⁶

The article considers the role of the state in ensuring sustainable development of tourism in Uzbekistan. In the conditions of innovative development of the economy, sustainable development of tourism occurs as a result of economic integration and the systematic improvement of international relations. With the innovative development of the economy, the role and prestige of tourism in the national economy is growing. Tourism is one of the most profitable sectors of the economy.⁷

Today richness of Uzbek terminology is mainly due to the use of other languages and word formation is giving. The main factor that determines the stability of a particular terminological system in a particular field is its regularity.⁸

The communicative method as the ultimate goal of learning involves the formation of communicative competence, which consists of linguistic, speech, subject, socio-cultural, educational and compensatory competencies.⁹

The main purpose of teaching computer graphics in school in the article is to teach students the order and rules of computer-aided drawing of graphic information, such as drawings, diagrams and schemes, performed in the disciplines of drawing and engineering graphics.¹⁰

This article is devoted to the study of Somerset Maugham’s short story “The Book Bag”. It mainly focuses on the analysis of moral and immoral issues, emphasizing to the matter of incest and its fatal outcomes.¹¹

The article considers the correlation of the real facts and imagination in “Tamburlaine the Great” by Christopher Marlowe.¹²

⁵ Najmutdinova, D. K., Nurmukhamedova, L. S., Alieva, D. A., Maksudova, D. S., & Nosirova, Z. A. (2016). Study of the effects of the age at menopause and duration of menopause on bone mineral density in postmenopausal women in Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Biomedicine*, 6(1), 38-40.

⁶ Turaeva, K., & Zarinabonu, A. (2022). Interpretation Of Woman Image in Modern Uzbek Literature (Based on Utkir Khashimov’s Book “Between Two Doors”). *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 4, 42-44.

⁷ Abdullaeva, A. A., & Kizi, K. D. R. (2020). Role of the state in ensuring sustainable development of tourism. *European science*, (1 (50)).

⁸ Bakhtiyorovna, N. M., & Zoirovna, N. I. Terms and Terminology in the Uzbek and English Languages. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(1), 173-176.

⁹ Абдуллаева, Л. С., Самадова, С. А., & Махмурова, М. (2014). Современные методы преподавания иностранных языков. *Коммуникативный метод. Наука. Мысль: электронный периодический журнал*, (6), 73-76.

¹⁰ Ruzimurodova, Z., & Mamatov, D. K. (2021). PECULIARITIES OF THE USE OF COMPUTER TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING ENGINEERING GRAPHICS. *World Bulletin of Social Sciences*, 4(11), 136-140.

¹¹ Pulatova, S. (2021). SUPERIORITY OF MORAL IDEAS AND FATAL RESULTS OF IMMORALITY IN THE SHORT STORY OF SOMERSET MAUGHAM “THE BOOK BAG”. *Збірник наукових праць ЛОГОС*.

Synonyms are formed from the combination of the Greek words syn" together"+ onoma" name", which is an important means of increasing the effectiveness of speech, a clearer, more vivid, logical and diverse expression of thought.¹³

The nature of the semantic volume of the word, language corpus and creating Uzbek language corpus is under the analysis of this article. This issue of principle importance for semasiological research has been interpreted in different ways in linguistics.¹⁴

This article covers the main place of small business and business in today's market economy. Including scientifically analyzed the development of small business and business, and the legal basis, at this time financially support small business and business, the latter is amended and the rules for this branch of national legislation are added.¹⁵

In the national economy, as in the economic systems of a number of foreign countries, the concept of public-private partnership (PPP) is being actively implemented.¹⁶

This article discusses the socio-philosophical importance of gender equality in today's increasingly globalized world. At the same time, in Uzbekistan, which is developing rapidly in all directions, the current issues of women's legal freedoms, protection of their legitimate interests, social relations of women in society and the development of society, social cohesion, family, traditions, It has been scientifically stated that culture, international and inter-civilizational relations, religion, labor and organization of public organizations are of great importance.¹⁷

All in all, each action has its own mysterious root. Definitely, Somerset Maugham managed to show this conception skillfully only with three heroes. Expressing "black door" which leads to "white hall" is given in a rather influential way so that this immortalizes the short story to eternity. Furthermore, it encourages prospective students to hear the story of true friends who always help each other forever in difficult times.

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4. Somerset Maugham. *Casuarina Tree*. A Collection of short stories. London.-1994.

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¹² Temirovna, M. P. (2021). THE CORRELATION OF HISTORICAL TRUTH AND IMAGINATION IN CHRISTOPHER MARLOWE'S TRAGEDY "TAMBURLAINE THE GREAT". *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 2(12), 455-457.

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